

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

D3.6 MANUAL FOR CARBON SEQUESTRATION MONITORING

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D3.6 MANUAL FOR CARBON SEQUESTRATION MONITORING

GUIDELINE FOR AN IMPROVED, WIDELY APPLICABLE, CS-SUITABLE MONITORING SCHEME
FOR CARBON SEQUESTRATION

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Abstract	This manual provides a structured guideline for assessing carbon sequestration capacity in wetland ecosystems within the Restore4Life project, with the aim of supporting a widely applicable and citizen science (CS)-suitable monitoring scheme. It compiles and evaluates a selection of field-based and geospatial methods, presented through standardised factsheets that describe their applicability, requirements, and limitations. The manual applies a transparent evaluation framework based on measurement characteristics and process-scale to support method comparison and selection. It highlights that individual methods capture only specific components of the carbon cycle and therefore represent partial estimates of carbon sequestration, requiring careful interpretation and, where appropriate, combination of approaches. Practical guidance is provided to support method selection.
Keywords	carbon sequestration, wetland monitoring, citizen science, biomass accumulation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Wetlands play a key role in climate regulation through their capacity to sequester carbon, yet assessing this function remains challenging due to the complexity of underlying processes and uncertainty and limited comparability of available methods. There is a need for an overview of existing approaches that enables users to navigate and compare methods for assessing wetland carbon sequestration.

This deliverable provides a structured manual compiling and evaluating methods for assessing carbon sequestration monitoring in wetland ecosystems within the Restore4Life project. It includes a selection of field-based and geospatial approaches, presented in standardized factsheets that describe their applicability, indicators, required data and equipment, as well as strengths, limitations, and practical considerations. The methods are assessed using a transparent evaluation framework based on measurement characteristics (e.g. accuracy, expertise, time, and costs) and process-scale (temporal and spatial resolution), enabling a consistent comparison and a targeted selection of approaches.

The manual highlights that individual methods capture only specific components of the carbon cycle and therefore represent partial estimates rather than complete carbon balances. As a result, the interpretation of results requires careful consideration of what each method measures, its assumptions, and its limitations. The document provides general guidance on method selection and application, emphasising the importance of consistent use over time and the need to align methods with specific monitoring objectives and constraints.

The manual does not aim to provide a complete accounting framework or a fully operational monitoring protocol. Instead, it offers a structured overview of available methods and their characteristics, supporting scientists, practitioners, and decision-makers in understanding, comparing, and selecting approaches for assessing carbon sequestration capacity in wetland ecosystems, including in contexts where citizen science may contribute to data collection.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	9
1.1	Aim of the manual.....	9
1.2	Conceptual background.....	10
1.2.1	Carbon sequestration capacity in wetlands: definitions and key terms	10
1.2.2	Carbon sequestration in wetlands: processes involved	11
1.2.3	Carbon assessment in wetlands: specific challenges.....	12
1.2.4	Carbon monitoring in wetlands: implications and interpretation.....	13
1.3	Citizen science in wetland carbon monitoring: opportunities and limitations	14
2	METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE MANUAL	16
2.1	Overview and classification of methods.....	16
2.2	Evaluation framework	17
3	OVERVIEW AND ASSESSMENT OF SELECTED CARBON SEQUESTRATION MONITORING METHODS.....	18
4	SYNTHESIS AND PRACTICAL GUIDANCE FOR APPLICATION	21
4.1	Citizen science suitability and emerging approaches.....	22
APPENDIX A: FACTSHEETS		25
RCSF1 Dendrometer band monitoring		26
RCSF2 Increment core analysis		28
RCSF3 Tree biomass (height & circumference)		30
RCSF4 Tree inventory (repeated measurements)		32
RCSF5 Sediment trap monitoring		34
RCSF6 Soil / sediment core analysis (radioisotopes dating)		36
RCSF7 Chamber CO ₂ / CH ₄ fluxes		38
RCSF8 ICOS / FLUXNET		40
RCSF9 Tea bag index		42
RCSF10 Litter traps		44
RCSG1 Land-cover-based assessments/ InVEST model		46
RCSG2 Remote sensing (Spectral, LiDAR, and DEM data)		48

ABBREVIATIONS

AGB	Aboveground Biomass
C	Carbon
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CS	Citizen Science
DBH	Diameter at breast height
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
ΔC	Change in carbon balance
ES	Ecosystem Services
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPP	Gross Primary Production
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs
LULC	Land Use/Land Cover
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NEE	Net Ecosystem Exchange
NEP	Net Ecosystem Production
NPP	Net Primary Production
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SOM	Soil Organic Matter
TOC	Total Organic Carbon

1 INTRODUCTION

Restore4Life (Restoration of wetland complexes as life supporting systems in the Danube Basin, project 101112736) is a Horizon Europe-funded project that supports the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. The Mission aims to protect and restore the health of our aquatic systems through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The Mission’s new approach treats the ocean and other water bodies as one interconnected system and plays a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Restore4Life aims to develop a “Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Decision Support System” at the Danube Basin level. This service is based on a shared vision for wetland restoration, including co-creation and co-development of tools that will enable local stakeholders and decision-makers to be actively involved in restoration works and help local businesses adopt new strategies through nature-based solutions.

Within the Restore4Life monitoring and assessment framework, monitoring plays a central role in evaluating the effectiveness of restoration measures and supporting adaptive management. In particular, the assessment of carbon-related ecosystem functions is essential for understanding the contribution of wetlands to climate regulation. Wetlands are important carbon sinks, and their restoration has significant potential to enhance the accumulation of carbon in above- and belowground biomass and in soil pools.

1.1 AIM OF THE MANUAL

This manual (Deliverable D3.6) provides a structured and practical framework for assessing carbon sequestration capacity in wetland ecosystems within the Restore4Life project. It aims to support the development of an improved, widely applicable monitoring scheme across different wetland types and restoration contexts.

The manual is embedded within Work Package 3 (WP3), particularly Task 3.3, and contributes to the overall Restore4Life monitoring framework. It complements Deliverable D3.5 (Assessment Indicator Toolbox; Wahl et al. 2026), which provides a broad selection of cost-effective and widely applicable methods and indicators for assessing ecosystem services in wetlands. While D3.5 includes methods for assessing carbon stocks, it does not cover carbon sequestration, which is addressed in this dedicated manual. Accordingly, this manual focuses on carbon sequestration capacity, i.e. the dynamic process of carbon accumulation and degradation as well as its fluxes in vegetation, sediment and soils.

The manual compiles a selection of methods that are applicable under different environmental and practical conditions including both field-based and geospatial approaches. The focus is on methods that are cost-effective, widely applicable and suitable for implementation by different user groups, including scientists, practitioners and, where appropriate, citizen scientists. The core of the manual consists of standardised method factsheets, which provide concise and comparable information on individual monitoring approaches. Each factsheet includes a concise description of the method, its applicability and contextual information (e.g. habitat type, indicator and carbon flow), as well as required

data and equipment. In addition, it provides a structured evaluation of measurement characteristics (citizen science suitability, accuracy, required expertise, time effort and costs) and the process-scale of the method, including its temporal and spatial resolution. Strengths, limitations and practical recommendations are summarised, and references to relevant sources following the general structure established in D3.5.

It should be noted that this manual does not aim to provide detailed laboratory protocols or highly specialised scientific procedures, which often require specific infrastructure and expertise. Thus, references to more detailed protocols and methodological guidance are provided in the factsheets. Instead, the focus is on providing a consistent and user-oriented overview of applicable methods for monitoring carbon sequestration in wetland ecosystems, including highly specialized methods only if necessary.

1.2 CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

Carbon sequestration in wetlands results from the interaction of biological production, organic matter accumulation, decomposition, greenhouse gas emissions and lateral carbon transport. Wetlands are therefore not only important carbon storage systems, but also highly dynamic biogeochemical systems whose role in climate regulation depends on the balance of multiple processes operating at different spatial and temporal scales.

1.2.1 CARBON SEQUESTRATION CAPACITY IN WETLANDS: DEFINITIONS AND KEY TERMS

Carbon sequestration capacity refers to the ability of a wetland ecosystem to take up carbon and retain it over time in biomass and soils. It is therefore a process-based concept describing the net change in stored carbon over time, rather than the amount of carbon stored at a given point in time (**carbon stocks**). This distinction is essential, as wetlands may contain large carbon stocks, while current carbon sequestration is low, neutral, or even negative. Conceptually, carbon sequestration capacity is determined by the balance between carbon inputs and carbon outputs and can therefore be expressed as:

$$\Delta C = \text{carbon inputs} - \text{carbon outputs}$$

A **positive carbon flux**, indicated by a negative ΔC , occurs when an ecosystem, region, or human activity releases more carbon (usually as CO_2 and CH_4) into the atmosphere than it absorbs. It acts as a **net carbon source**, increasing atmospheric concentration and accelerating global warming. In contrast, a **negative carbon flux**, indicated by a positive ΔC , exists when an ecosystem acts as **net carbon sink**, storing more carbon than it releases.

The balance between carbon inputs and outputs results from the interaction of different **carbon pools** and **carbon fluxes** within the ecosystem. **Carbon pools** are ecosystem compartments, which have the capacity to store and release carbon. The main carbon pools in wetlands are biomass (wetland forests, dead wood, roots) and soils (organic or mineral), with their relative importance depending on the wetland type (e.g. peatlands, marshes,

floodplain forests). These pools may differ in both their stability and turnover rates. These pools are interconnected through carbon fluxes between vegetation, soils, the atmosphere and the hydrosphere. **Carbon fluxes** are defined as the amount and direction of carbon exchanged between carbon pools.

The resulting **carbon sequestration rate** reflects the net outcome of these interacting processes over time and can be expressed as **ΔC per unit area and time** (e.g. $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$).

However, a wetland's carbon sequestration rate does not necessarily reflect its overall climatic impact. For example, a wetland may show significant organic carbon accumulation yet have a high global warming potential due to substantial GHG emissions. The **global warming potential (GWP)** is a measure of how much energy (heat) the emission of 1 ton of a gas will absorb over a given time period (usually 100 years), relative to the emission of 1 ton of CO_2 (EPA, 2025). The larger the GWP, the more a given gas warms the Earth compared to CO_2 over that period. In addition to CO_2 , significant emissions of CH_4 (methane) and N_2O (nitrous oxide) may occur in wetlands. Methane is estimated to have a GWP of 27–30 over 100 years. Nitrous Oxide (N_2O), which is not accounted for in carbon fluxes, has a GWP 273 times greater than that of CO_2 over a 100-year timescale. Positive (greenhouse gas emissions) and negative (carbon sequestration) carbon fluxes may occur simultaneously. In practice, the full carbon balance (ΔC) is rarely measured directly, due to the complexity of these interacting processes. Instead, individual components of the carbon cycle are often used as proxies for carbon sequestration, such as biomass accumulation, soil carbon changes over time or specific flux measurements. These approaches capture only part of the overall carbon balance and therefore represent approximations rather than complete system assessments. For this reason, the terms **sink and source** as well as **carbon sequestration rates/capacities** should always be interpreted with reference to the specific variable considered, the system boundary and the assessment time. **A statement on wetland carbon sequestration alone does not automatically capture the system's full impact on global climate change.**

1.2.2 CARBON SEQUESTRATION IN WETLANDS: PROCESSES INVOLVED

The carbon dynamics of wetlands are determined by the interaction of multiple inputs and outputs of carbon. Natural carbon **inputs** (gains) include photosynthetic uptake of atmospheric CO_2 (**Gross Primary Production, GPP**), and the transfer of organic matter to soils via litter production and root turnover, as well as external inputs through sediment deposition of inflowing water. Natural carbon **outputs** (losses) include **respiration** during decomposition and mineralisation processes, ultimately leading to **greenhouse gas emissions** (including methane production under anaerobic conditions), and **lateral transport** of dissolved and particulate carbon (Villa & Bernal, 2018). The **Net Primary Production (NPP)** is the remaining plant carbon gain after plant respiration ($\text{GPP} - \text{autotrophic respiration by plants}$), while the **Net Ecosystem Production (NEP)** is the difference between GPP and total ecosystem respiration, including both autotrophic respiration by plants and heterotrophic respiration by microorganisms and other decomposers. Additionally, organic carbon can be removed through harvesting (**human outputs**).

Wetlands capture atmospheric CO₂ through plant photosynthesis and convert it into aboveground biomass and roots. This organic material is subsequently transferred to the soil through litter fall and root turnover, contributing to the formation of **soil organic matter (SOM)** of which **soil organic carbon (SOC)** is the carbon component commonly measured in soil analyses. In many wetland systems, this process is further supported by sedimentation and accretion, which promote the burial of organic material and thus enhance long-term carbon storage (Were et al., 2019). Carbon sequestration in such systems is therefore closely linked to the accumulation of organic matter and can, in practical terms, be related to the combined effects of soil carbon content, bulk density, and accretion rates (Villa & Bernal, 2018). Under waterlogged conditions, reduced oxygen availability slows aerobic decomposition, allowing organic matter to persist over long-time scales. At the same time, anaerobic decomposition processes can produce methane (CH₄), reducing the net climate benefit associated with carbon accumulation.

Overall, carbon sequestration in wetlands is determined by the balance among plant-derived organic carbon production, decomposition, sediment dynamics, and site-specific environmental conditions such as hydrology, temperature, and nutrient availability, as well as human activities.

1.2.3 CARBON ASSESSMENT IN WETLANDS: SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

Spatial heterogeneity: Carbon stocks and sequestration rates vary substantially not only between wetland types (e.g. peatlands, marshes, floodplain forests), but also within individual sites. Small-scale differences in water level, vegetation structure, sediment deposition, and micro-topography can lead to strong spatial variability in biomass production, soil carbon accumulation, and organic matter inputs. As most methods rely on sample- or plot-based measurements, this spatial heterogeneity makes it difficult to derive representative values and to upscale results to the site or landscape level.

Temporal variability: Carbon-related processes respond rapidly to changes in hydrology, temperature and vegetation dynamics, resulting in variability across multiple temporal scales, ranging from short-term fluctuations to seasonal, interannual, and decadal dynamics. At the same time, the methods applied capture processes over very different temporal scales, ranging from short-term measurements (e.g. soil fluxes) to long-term accumulation (e.g. dendrometer). This makes it difficult to relate short-term observations to longer-term sequestration trends and increases the risk of misinterpretation if the temporal context is not explicitly considered.

Methodological uncertainty and limited comparability: Due to the diversity of methods used, approaches differ in whether they quantify carbon inputs, outputs, or changes in specific pools, and therefore represent only parts of the overall carbon balance. Many field-based approaches, such as biomass-based or soil-based methods, rely on indirect estimates and additional assumptions (e.g. allometric formulas or accumulation rates). In contrast, geospatial approaches often derive carbon-related indicators from remote-sensing data or spatial models, which require calibration and validation using field data. Geospatial approaches may improve spatial coverage, but introduce additional uncertainty related to model assumptions and input data quality. As a result, different methods may produce

substantially different estimates of carbon sequestration due to differences in scale, data sources, and underlying assumptions. This limits comparability across methods and requires careful interpretation of what each method actually represents.

1.2.4 CARBON MONITORING IN WETLANDS: IMPLICATIONS AND INTERPRETATION

The challenges outlined above have direct implications for monitoring design and data interpretation.

Indicator- and process-specific interpretation: Methods quantify different indicators (e.g. biomass growth, soil carbon accumulation, or fluxes) and represent specific components of the carbon cycle rather than the full carbon balance. Results should therefore be interpreted in relation to the respective ΔC captured by the method.

Transferability and upscaling limitations: Due to spatial heterogeneity and site-specific conditions, results derived at the sample or plot level are not easily transferable to larger spatial units. Upscaling requires careful consideration of the environmental context and may introduce additional uncertainty.

Process-scale dependency (temporal and spatial scale): The interpretability of results depends strongly on the process scale represented by the data. Methods differ in their temporal resolution (e.g. from hours to years or decades) and spatial scale (e.g. sample, plot, or landscape level), which defines the scope of the information they provide. As a result, outputs from different methods are not directly comparable without explicitly considering their respective temporal and spatial context.

Uncertainty related to method requirements and assumptions: Differences in required data, equipment, and methodological assumptions (e.g. allometric relationships, accumulation rates, or model inputs) lead to substantial variation in results. Furthermore, methods are sensitive to the level of expertise required for data collection, processing, and interpretation. Variability in application, operator decisions, or data handling can therefore cause additional uncertainty. To ensure interpretability and comparability, method-specific requirements, assumptions, and procedures must be explicitly documented.

Method combination: A comprehensive assessment of carbon sequestration requires the combination of complementary approaches. Field measurements and geospatial analyses provide different types of information, levels of detail, and spatial coverage, and should be interpreted jointly to improve robustness and completeness.

These implications highlight the need for a structured and transparent comparison of methods, in which their respective scope, limitations, and applicability are clearly described. The factsheets presented in this manual address this need by systematically compiling key information on different approaches, including their measurement characteristics (e.g. accuracy, expertise, time, and costs), process-scale relevance, and practical requirements.

1.3 CITIZEN SCIENCE IN WETLAND CARBON MONITORING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS

Citizen science has **considerable potential to support measurements and estimates** of carbon sequestration in wetlands, but it also comes with structural limitations. The balance between the two depends heavily on how projects are designed and validated. The following sections outline the opportunities and challenges of citizen science for monitoring wetland carbon sequestration.

The main **opportunities** of citizen science for wetland carbon monitoring include:

Large-scale data collection at low cost. Carbon sequestration varies widely across ecosystems such as forests, soils, and wetlands, creating a need for spatially extensive and repeated observations. Professional monitoring alone is expensive and limited in both spatial and temporal coverage. Citizen scientists can collect data across large geographic areas, monitor local changes over time, and increase sampling frequency dramatically.

Local knowledge and long-term engagement. Participants often have deep familiarity with their local environments. This helps identify subtle ecological changes (e.g., soil quality, vegetation shifts), maintain long-term monitoring plots, and improve contextual interpretation of data. For carbon sequestration, this is especially useful in tracking land-use changes and forest growth.

Education and behavioural impact. Citizen science can increase climate literacy, encouraging sustainable land management, and building public support for climate policies. This social impact is crucial, even if the scientific precision is imperfect.

Integration with new technologies. Smartphones, GPS, and low-cost sensors allow citizens to measure tree diameter and estimate biomass, identify tree species, upload geotagged photos, and use apps linked to remote sensing data. When combined with satellite systems (e.g., Copernicus Earth observation programme), citizen data can help validate large-scale carbon models.

However, the involvement of citizen scientists for estimating carbon sequestration also has its **limits and challenges:**

Data quality and consistency. The main challenges are the different skill levels among participants and measurement errors (e.g., tree height, soil carbon sampling) due to insufficient training. Carbon sequestration estimates are sensitive to small measurement errors, which can propagate into large uncertainties. Citizen Science requires detailed data quality control protocols before (e.g., easy-to-follow protocols, training, etc.) and during data

collection, as well as data cleaning procedures before analyses. Without validation frameworks, the data may not be usable for formal carbon accounting.

Lack of standardization. Scientific carbon accounting requires strict protocols. Citizen projects often struggle with ensuring everyone follows the same method, maintaining calibration across tools and users, and preventing biased sampling (e.g., people choosing “interesting” sites).

Limited technical scope. Many aspects of carbon sequestration are hard to measure without advanced equipment. Soil organic carbon requires lab analysis, below-ground biomass is difficult to estimate, and flux measurements (CO₂ exchange) need specialised instruments. Citizen science is better suited to proxy indicators (like tree growth) than direct measurement. Also, the calculation and interpretation of carbon sequestration rates require trained experts.

Participation bias and retention. Citizen science tends to attract more participants in urban or affluent regions. Activities take place mostly on the weekends during nice weather. Citizen Scientists prefer locations that are easy to access and/or easy to sample, which is rarely the case in wetlands. Also, long-term engagement can drop off, which affects the continuity of datasets.

2 METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE MANUAL

The manual is designed to help users select suitable methods for assessing carbon sequestration capacity based on their specific monitoring objectives, available infrastructure, expertise and resources.

The manual is organized in a systematic and structured manner to help users easily identify suitable approaches. It combines a process-based overview of methods (Chapter 3) with standardised factsheets, each providing concise and comparable information on individual approaches (Appendix A).

2.1 OVERVIEW AND CLASSIFICATION OF METHODS

Carbon sequestration in wetlands is a process-based phenomenon resulting from the interaction of carbon inputs, storage, transformation, and losses within the ecosystem. Individual methods capture specific components of these processes and therefore represent different elements of the overall carbon balance.

To facilitate the identification and comparison of methods, the manual is divided into 5 categories (C1–C5). Four categories comprise field-based measurements targeting specific carbon pools or processes:

- **C1** Plant biomass accumulation
- **C2** Soil/sediment accumulation
- **C3** Carbon gas fluxes
- **C4** Litterfall and decomposition

while one category groups geospatial modelling approaches:

- **C5** Geospatial modelling

Within these categories, the manual contains detailed information for each method, given in Table 1.

TABLE 1: ORGANIZATION OF THE C-SEQUESTRATION MANUAL

Method	Name of the method
Judgement (measurement characteristics)	Expert-based evaluation of the method, including suitability for citizen scientists, expected accuracy, required expertise, time requirements, and estimated costs
Indicator	Name of the indicator being measured
Units	Units related to the indicator
Process-scale	Temporal and spatial resolution span of the data produced by the method
ID	Unique identifier linking to the corresponding detailed factsheet, based on D3.5 ID format

2.2 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

To ensure a consistent and transparent comparison of methods, the manual applies a standardised evaluation framework based on the structure of the method factsheets. Each factsheet/method is assessed regarding two complementary dimensions:

- **measurement characteristics**, which describe the requirements and effort associated with the implementation of the method, and
- **process-scale**, which describes the temporal and spatial resolution of the data generated by the method.

The **measurement characteristics** cover the method's suitability for implementation by citizen scientists (CS), expected accuracy, the required level of expertise, time requirements, and estimated costs; the corresponding criteria and symbols are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2: EXPERT JUDGEMENT OF THE METHODS' PERFORMANCE

Category	Symbol	Meaning
CS suitability		Suitable for citizen scientists
		Unsuitable for citizen scientists
Accuracy of measurement		Low accuracy (>75% deviation/misclassified)
		Medium accuracy (50–75% deviation/misclassified)
		High accuracy (<25% deviation/misclassified)
Necessary expertise/training		No former training necessary
		Basic training necessary
		More intensive training necessary
Time requirement		Minutes
		Hours
		Days
Estimated costs	€	Free or with standard equipment (laptop, household items)
	€ €	<200€
	€ € €	>200€

The **process-scale** describes the temporal and spatial scale at which the method captures carbon sequestration processes. In contrast to measurement characteristics, the process-scale does not describe the effort required to apply a method, but the scope and interpretability of the results it produces. Temporal scales may range from short-term measurements (e.g. hours or days) to long-term observations (e.g. years or decades), while spatial scales may range from sample-level measurements to site- or landscape-scale assessments. The applicable categories are indicated by shading the corresponding cells:

Temporal

hours [h]	days [d]	months [mo]	years [yr]	decades [dec]
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Spatial

sample [samp]	plot [plot]	habitat type [hab]	site [site]	landscape [lscp]
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3 OVERVIEW AND ASSESSMENT OF SELECTED CARBON SEQUESTRATION MONITORING METHODS

Method	Judgement	Indicator	Units	Process-scale	ID
C1 Plant biomass accumulation (field measurements)					
Dendrometer band monitoring		Stem circumference increment Biomass increment	cm yr^{-1} $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	yr \sim dec samp \sim hab	RCSF1 page 26
Increment core analysis		Tree-ring width Biomass increment	mm yr^{-1} $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	yr \sim dec samp	RCSF2 page 28
Tree biomass (height & circumference)		Tree biomass carbon stock Change in biomass carbon stock	t C ha^{-1} $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}; \Delta\text{C}$	yr \sim dec samp	RCSF3 page 30
Tree inventory (repeated measurements)		Tree biomass carbon stock Change in carbon stock over time	t C ha^{-1} $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}; \Delta\text{C}$	yr \sim dec hab \sim site	RCSF4 page 32

C2 Soil / sediment accumulation (field measurements)					
Sediment trap monitoring		Sediment accretion rate Organic carbon burial rate Carbon sequestration rate	mm yr^{-1} $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	$\text{d} \sim \text{yr}$ samp \sim lscp	RCSF5 page 34
Soil / sediment core analysis (radioisotopes dating)		Sediment accretion rate Organic carbon accumulation / burial rate	mm yr^{-1} $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	$\text{yr} \sim \text{dec}$ samp \sim site	RCSF6 page 36
C3 Carbon gas fluxes (field measurements)					
Chamber CO ₂ / CH ₄ fluxes		CO ₂ / CH ₄ fluxes	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2/\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\text{h} \sim \text{yr}$ samp \sim site	RCSF7 page 38
ICOS / FLUXNET				$\text{h} \sim \text{dec}$ plot \sim lscp	RCSF8 page 40

C4 Litterfall and decomposition (field measurements)					
Tea bag index		Decomposition rate constant Stabilization factor Mass loss	k, day^{-1} $S, \text{unitless}$ $\% \text{ or } \text{g g}^{-1} \text{time}^{-1}$	$h \sim \text{yr}$ $\text{samp} \sim \text{plot}$	RCSF9 page 42
Litter traps		Annual litterfall production Aboveground litter carbon input	$\text{Mg dry mass ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$	$h \sim \text{yr}$ $\text{samp} \sim \text{hab}$	RCSF10 page 44
C5 Geospatial modelling					
Land-cover-based assessments/ InVEST model		Change in carbon stocks	$\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}; \Delta C$	$\text{yr} \sim \text{dec}$ $\text{site} \sim \text{lscp}$	RCSG1 page 46
Remote sensing (Spectral, LiDAR, and DEM data)		Above-ground biomass (AGB) Change in AGB Above-ground carbon stock change	Mg ha^{-1} $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}; \Delta C$	$\text{yr} \sim \text{dec}$ $\text{hab} \sim \text{lscp}$	RCSG2 page 48

4 SYNTHESIS AND PRACTICAL GUIDANCE FOR APPLICATION

Methods used to assess carbon sequestration differ fundamentally in what they measure and in the timescales they represent. Some approaches quantify changes in carbon stored in specific **pools** (aboveground biomass, belowground biomass, dead organic matter, soils), while others measure **exchanges** of greenhouse gases with the atmosphere. **Gas flux measurements** can provide information over **short periods** (seconds to months) but are often variable. **Changes in biomass and soils** accumulate more slowly and generally require **multi-year observations** to detect trends.

As a practical guideline for temporal coverage, gas flux measurements should span multiple seasons and preferably at least 2–3 years to capture interannual variability. Tree growth and woody biomass should be monitored over multiple years (at least 3–5 years) to reduce short-term noise, with faster-growing vegetation re-measured more frequently than slower-growing vegetation. **Soil or peat carbon change**, as well as **sediment accretion**, should be assessed over **multi-year** to decadal intervals. Accordingly, **accuracy** depends on the chosen method, the level of expertise, and the quality of equipment and data. To ensure **comparability** over time, the same methods, protocols, and data sources should be applied consistently across years, with clear units (e.g., $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ or $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$) and an explicit sign convention (plus or minus).

No single method captures the full carbon balance. Measurements of above-ground biomass, for example, do not include below-ground dynamics, greenhouse gas emissions, or lateral carbon transport. Conversely, gas flux measurements do not represent long-term storage in soils and biomass. Methods should therefore be used in a **complementary** manner. A comprehensive assessment combines a limited set of approaches that, together, cover the main components of the carbon cycle relevant to the site and the monitoring objective. Results must be **interpreted within clearly defined boundaries**. It should be specified which carbon pools and gases are included, the spatial extent and soil depth considered, and whether lateral transport (dissolved or particulate carbon) is accounted for. These principles support consistent application of the methods presented in this manual and provide a basis for selecting complementary approaches.

When monitoring results are intended for use in **climate mitigation frameworks**, including carbon accounting and carbon credit schemes, substantially higher requirements apply. Partial estimates derived from individual methods are not sufficient unless they are embedded within a consistent accounting framework. This requires explicit definition of system boundaries, inclusion of all relevant carbon pools and fluxes, and long-term, consistent datasets to account for temporal variability. Given these requirements, most methods presented in this manual are not directly applicable for these purposes without additional modelling, integration, and validation steps. For this purpose, the **2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories**, as well as their supplements (from 2013) and refinements (from 2019), provide a widely accepted methodological framework for

estimating greenhouse gas emissions and removals. These guidelines are based on a tiered approach, ranging from default emission factors (Tier 1) to country-specific data and models (Tiers 2 and 3). While they ensure methodological transparency, comparability, and completeness at national scales, their application at project or site level is often limited by high data demands, the need for extensive calibration and validation, and the requirement to account for all relevant flux components, including non-carbon greenhouse gases. Therefore, the IPCC Guidelines provide an important **methodological reference**, but they do not replace site-specific monitoring protocols for wetland restoration projects.

In addition to the methods compiled in this manual, several initiatives are currently working on improving the assessment of **carbon sequestration** and **GHG fluxes** in wetlands. Regarding carbon storage and GHG fluxes in coastal wetlands, the EU project **Restore4Cs** provides additional products such as webinars and methodological manuals (<https://www.restore4cs.eu/>, Minaudo et al. 2023).

For practical application, method selection should start with a clear definition of the monitoring objective. Users should ask:

- Should the method measure a carbon pool, a flux, or a proxy?
- Does it address the actual monitoring objective?
- **Can it be repeated consistently over the years?**
- Are the required expertise, equipment, and costs realistic?

If the aim is full carbon accounting, no single factsheet is sufficient. A combination of methods and expert interpretation is required.

4.1 CITIZEN SCIENCE SUITABILITY AND EMERGING APPROACHES

Citizen science is most effective when it is complementary, not stand-alone. Strong use cases include forest inventory (tree species, diameter, density), monitoring restoration projects, ground-truthing satellite carbon estimates, and detecting land-use changes over time. Citizen science is less suitable for detailed carbon quantification without laboratory support, and greenhouse gas measurements.

Citizen science can significantly expand the scale and social relevance of carbon sequestration research, but it cannot fully replace professional measurement systems. Its greatest value lies in enhancing datasets, filling spatial and temporal gaps, and engaging the public in climate solutions. The key is hybrid systems—combining citizen observations, expert oversight, and remote sensing—to balance scale resolution, and accuracy.

Recently, **smartphone-based photography** has been explored as a low-cost and low-effort citizen science approach for monitoring Green Leaf Phenology (GLP) in peatlands (Davidson et al. 2025). Digital red–green–blue (RGB), time-stamped and geo-tagged smartphone photos can be used as a non-destructive method for monitoring GLP, greenness indices (dimensionless, RGB-based), and day of year (DOY) at peak greenness. Thus, citizen scientists can provide useful information on changes in peatland vegetation phenology and peatland condition over longer time periods. While carbon fluxes or biomass changes are not directly measured, GLP may be related to plant growth and carbon uptake; however, reliable correlations between these parameters have not been established to date. The method for monitoring GLP is also not yet standardised and requires calibration, validation, and methodological development.

Similar limitations apply to emerging citizen science approaches estimating soil organic carbon from soil photographs (Heil et al. 2022) or simplified assessments of organic matter content. These methods may provide supporting information, but they are not yet sufficiently calibrated, validated, or robust for routine application. They should therefore be considered as **work-in-progress approaches** rather than established monitoring methods.

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APPENDIX A: FACTSHEETS

RCSF1 Dendrometer band monitoring	26
RCSF2 Increment core analysis	28
RCSF3 Tree biomass (height & circumference)	30
RCSF4 Tree inventory (repeated measurements)	32
RCSF5 Sediment trap monitoring	34
RCSF6 Soil / sediment core analysis (radioisotopes dating)	36
RCSF7 Chamber CO ₂ / CH ₄ fluxes	38
RCSF8 ICOS / FLUXNET	40
RCSF9 Tea bag index	42
RCSF10 Litter traps	44
RCSG1 Land-cover-based assessments/ InVEST model	46
RCSG2 Remote sensing (Spectral, LiDAR, and DEM data)	48

RCSF1

Dendrometer band monitoring

Timo Hartmann, Tudor Racoviceanu, Mathias Scholz, Ute Susanne Kaden

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Dendrometer band monitoring provides repeated measurements of tree stem circumference increment, allowing derivation of diameter increment and estimation of annual biomass increment and carbon accumulation in aboveground biomass at tree and stand level. Measurements are typically recorded at regular intervals, often annually after the growing season, and long-term datasets enable analysis of growth trends over decades.

A representative and statistically balanced sample of trees covering different species, size classes, and site conditions is required to ensure reliable estimates. Measurements are typically conducted above breast height and therefore require conversion to diameter at breast height (DBH, 1.30 m) using appropriate expansion factors or calibration measurements. Circumference increment must be converted to diameter increment.

Derived diameter increments are converted to biomass increments using allometric equations based on DBH and tree height. Since dendrometers measure only stem circumference change, height growth must be estimated using species-specific functions. Carbon accumulation is derived from the change in aboveground carbon stocks between consecutive years (e.g. $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

Habitat type: forests

Compartment: above-ground biomass

Indicator: Stem circumference/diameter increment (cm yr^{-1}); derived biomass increment ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)

C flow: delta

Required data:

- Tree species, stem circumference measurements, stand structure
- Allometric equations (species-specific or generalized)
- Optional: climate data (temperature, precipitation)
- Basic data processing tools (e.g., spreadsheets, statistical software)

<p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dendrometer bands (e.g., D1 type with spring mechanism) • Measuring tape / calipers (for DBH reference measurements) • Field marking and labeling materials • Ladder (at least 2 m) 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relatively simple and cost-effective method • Direct measurement of tree growth over time • Suitable for long-term monitoring • Can be applied in citizen science with basic training • Provides robust estimates of biomass increment when combined with allometry 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures only stem circumference change (height growth must be recorded in the field) • Requires conversion to DBH and use of allometric equations • Limited to woody vegetation (mainly trees) • Potential measurement errors due to installation or environmental factors • Upscaling from sample trees to stand introduces uncertainty • Needs technical maintenance and recording time in the field in winter once a year • First result after 2 years of installation
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure representative sampling across species, size classes, and site conditions • Standardise installation height and measurement intervals • Protect the dendrometer bands from vandalism by installing them at a sufficient height (e.g. 2.50 m) • Combine with periodic DBH measurements for calibration • Use appropriate allometric equations for the study region • Conduct regular maintenance and calibration of dendrometer bands • Maintain long-term monitoring to capture variability and trends 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>UNFCCC (2015). Measurements for Estimation of Carbon Stocks in Afforestation and Reforestation Project Activities under the Clean Development Mechanism: A Field Manual</p> <p>Zanne, A. E., Lopez-Gonzalez, G., Coomes, D. A., Ilic, J., Jansen, S., Lewis, S. L., ... & Chave, J. (2009). Data from: Towards a worldwide wood economics spectrum. <i>Dryad</i>. https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.234</p> <p>Zianis, D., Muukkonen, P., Mäkipää, R., & Mencuccini, M. (2005). Biomass and stem volume equations for tree species in Europe. <i>Silva Fennica Monographs</i>, 2005(4), 1–63. https://doi.org/10.14214/sf.sfm4</p>	

RCSF2

Increment core analysis

Timo Hartmann, Mathias Scholz, Ute Susanne Kaden

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Tree cores are extracted from tree stems using an increment borer, typically at a standardized height and ideally reaching the pith. The cores are dried and prepared by surface treatment, such as sanding, scraping, or microtome cutting, to ensure clear visibility of annual growth rings, which are then measured under laboratory conditions using specialized equipment. Tree-ring width measurements allow the reconstruction of annual radial growth over time. Based on these increments, diameter development is derived and, together with DBH and allometric relationships, used to estimate biomass increment and carbon accumulation. Where necessary, measured ring widths are related to DBH using appropriate transformation functions and additional field measurements. Carbon accumulation is derived from reconstructed biomass trajectories and annual growth increments, and can be extrapolated from tree to plot or stand level using representative sampling and grouping approaches.

In contrast to dendrometer monitoring, this method enables retrospective reconstruction of long-term growth dynamics and responses to environmental variability.

Habitat type: Forests

Compartment: above-ground biomass

Indicator: Tree-ring width (mm yr^{-1}); derived biomass increment ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$)

C flow: delta

Required data:

- Tree species, diameter measurements (DBH), and stand structure
- Allometric equations (species-specific or generalized)
- Optional: meteorological or hydrological data (e.g. temperature, precipitation)
- Data processing tools (e.g. dendrochronological or statistical software)

Required equipment:

- Increment borer (e.g. Mora-Coretax, ~5 mm diameter)
- Sample preparation tools (e.g. sanding equipment, razor blades, or microtome)
- Measurement system (e.g. microscope with measuring table such as LINTAB and software such as TSAP-Win)

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides high-resolution historical growth data from individual trees per year • Enables retrospective analysis of biomass increment and carbon accumulation • Allows linking growth dynamics to environmental drivers (e.g. droughts, floods) • Only one field campaign required for long-term reconstruction • Standardised and widely used in dendrochronology and forest ecology 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires specialised equipment and expertise for sample recording, preparation and ring-width measurement • Time-consuming and costly laboratory processing • Cores may not reach the pith, complicating age and growth reconstruction • Species-specific growth patterns and wood anatomy can affect measurement accuracy • Carbon estimates depend on additional allometric models and assumptions • Sampling may be limited by tree condition, accessibility, or conservation constraints • Potential damage to trees during sampling
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure representative sampling across species, size classes, and site conditions and standardise sampling height and core preparation procedures to ensure comparability and use sufficient sample sizes to reduce uncertainty in stand-level extrapolation • Combine increment core data with DBH measurements for accurate biomass estimation • Apply region- and species-specific allometric equations and interpret results in the context of environmental conditions and disturbance history • Carefully assess core quality (e.g. missing pith, reaction wood) before analysis 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Gärtner, H., & Nievergelt, D. (2010). The core-microtome: a new tool for surface preparation on cores and time series analysis of varying cell parameters. <i>Dendrochronologia</i>, 28(2), 85–92. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2009.09.002</p> <p>Schnabel, F., Purruicker, S., Schmitt, L., Engelmann, R. A., Kahl, A., Richter, R., ... & Wirth, C. (2022). Cumulative growth and stress responses to the 2018–2019 drought in a European floodplain forest. <i>Global change biology</i>, 28(5), 1870–1883. https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16028</p> <p>Shupe, H. A., Jensen, K., Oldeland, J., & Ludewig, K. (2022). Droughts decrease and floods increase carbon sequestration rates of <i>Quercus robur</i> in hardwood floodplain forests. <i>Trees, Forests and People</i>, 9, 100294. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tfp.2022.100294</p>	

RCSF3

Tree biomass monitoring for carbon stock change (ΔC) in floodplain forests

Gabriele Weigelhofer, Eva Feldbacher, Timo Hartmann

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Measurement to estimate biomass in forested areas, including both living trees and deadwood. Measuring tree circumference at breast height and tree height using the triangle method, a clinometer, or a smartphone application. Calculation of living and dead tree biomass and carbon stocks is performed using simple formulas based on tree species and wood density.

Repeated measurements of the same forested area over time allow for the estimation of changes in biomass and carbon stocks according to the stock change method as described in the 2006 IPCC report. The ΔC over the observation period is calculated by simply subtracting C_{total} at time 1 from C_{total} at time 2; C_{total} means here Total carbon stock of living tree and deadwood biomass. These changes can be interpreted as the Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) over the observation period. The Net Primary Production (NPP) is the amount of biomass that trees annually produce by photosynthesis and can e. g. also be expressed as $\Delta C_{living\ trees}$.

Habitat type: forests

Compartment: above-ground biomass

Indicators: Tree biomass carbon stock ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$); Change in biomass carbon stock (ΔC ; $t\ C\ ha^{-1}$ over time period)

C flow: delta

Required data:

- Tree circumference (DBH proxy, the diameter at both ends and the diameter at the center of lying deadwood or diameters of the cross-sections at tree stump)
- Tree height or tree length (lying deadwood)
- Tree species
- Wood density / allometric parameters
- Plot area and tree positions
- Repeated measurements of the same trees (tree labeling required)

<p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring tape • Stick, clinometer, or tree height app • Tree marking and labeling materials 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to apply • Low costs • Suitable for citizen science • Non-destructive method • High precision of growth rate estimates possible 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree height estimates are difficult in dense forests, on uneven ground, and on slopes • Tree height apps are prone to error if not used correctly and calibrated • Limited possibility for citizen scientists to verify measurement accuracy • Time- and labor-intensive field campaigns with required repetition • Small changes over short time periods may be within measurement uncertainty
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We recommend the triangle method for measuring tree height. With little training, this method is more reliable than using apps and gives better results in the field. Clinometers can also yield accurate data if used correctly. • Record and label measured trees to allow repeated measurements and comparison over time • Use consistent measurement protocols (same height, same method) across time steps • Repeated measurements enable estimation of carbon stock changes (ΔC), which can be interpreted as above-ground carbon sequestration • Combine with complementary methods (e.g. soil carbon measurements) for a more complete carbon balance 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>IPCC 2006, 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Prepared by the National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme, Eggleston H.S., Buendia L., Miwa K., Ngara T. and Tanabe K. (eds). Published: IGES, Japan.</p> <p>Pretzsch, H. (2009). <i>Forest Dynamics, Growth and Yield</i>. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-88307-4</p> <p>UNFCCC. (2015a): AR-TOOL14 Methodological tool: Estimation of carbon stocks and change in carbon stocks of trees and shrubs in A/R CDM project activities. Version 04.2.</p> <p>Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., & Cvijanović, D. (2025). Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists – Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328601</p> <p>Zianis, D., Muukkonen, P., Mäkipää, R., & Mencuccini, M. (2005). Biomass and stem volume equations for tree species in Europe. <i>Silva Fennica Monographs</i>, 2005(4), 1–63. https://doi.org/10.14214/sf.sfm4</p>	

RCSF4

Repeated tree inventory measurements

Marie Wahl, Krisztina Gulyás, Timo Hartmann, Mathias Scholz

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs
	€			

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Carbon stocks in forests can be estimated using local tree inventories. Forest inventories from official forest management units should include, at a minimum, information on tree species, age classes, area covered by each species, and yield per species or age class. This information allows for the calculation of timber volume per species and/or age class. Using the wood densities of tree species, the aboveground biomass can be estimated, and carbon stock can be assumed to be as approximately 50% of biomass. If forest inventory data from multiple time points are available, changes in carbon stocks can be calculated and interpreted as carbon sequestration (ΔC) over the respective time period.

Habitat type: forests

Compartment: above-ground biomass

Indicator:

Carbon stock ($t C ha^{-1}$)

Change in carbon stock (ΔC ; $t C ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$)

C flow: delta

Required data

- Local forest inventory data (tree species, age classes, area, yield/volume) for at least two different years
- Wood density values (e.g. Wood Density Database)
- Forest inventory data from at least two time steps (for ΔC estimation)

Required equipment:

- GIS software (optional, for spatial analysis)
- Spreadsheet software (e.g. MS Excel)

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High reliability of data quality (official inventories) • High accuracy for above-ground biomass estimates • Low cost if data are accessible • Large spatial coverage (management unit to regional scale) 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data are usually not open access • Often only aggregated data available (no raw tree-level data) • Potentially long data request times • Inventory methods may differ between time steps, affecting comparability • May not include all biomass components (e.g. deadwood), leading to biased estimations • Growth rates in forest management plans are often based on conventional calculation methods, that causes overestimations
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest inventories can be requested from local forest management units; availability and accessibility vary by region • Repeated inventories enable estimation of carbon stock changes (ΔC), which can be interpreted as carbon sequestration • Report sequestration by converting net increases in carbon stocks to CO_2: compute ΔC ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) and multiply by $44/12 \approx 3.667$ to obtain $\text{t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ • Differences in inventory methods, aggregation levels, and reporting formats between time steps should be carefully considered • Verify biomass expansion factors and carbon fractions with local authorities where possible • Inventory data may be aggregated due to confidentiality; interpretation should consider potential underestimation of total biomass (e.g. 10–15%) • Combine with field measurements or remote sensing data where possible to improve accuracy 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Zanne, A. E., Lopez-Gonzalez, G., Coomes, D. A., Ilic, J., Jansen, S., Lewis, S. L., ... & Chave, J. (2009). Data from: Towards a worldwide wood economics spectrum. <i>Dryad</i>. https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.234</p>	

RCSF5

Sediment trap monitoring

Ute Susanne Kaden, Mathias Scholz

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Sediment deposition in floodplain ecosystems is quantified using marker horizons, sediment traps, or sediment mats installed at representative sites along hydrogeomorphic gradients. These methods allow repeated measurements of vertical sediment accretion or event-based sediment deposition over defined time intervals. Sediment mats are artificial surfaces, such as artificial turf or geotextile, that are secured on the soil surface. During inundation or flood events, suspended sediment settles and is collected after defined intervals or events.

The deposited material is analysed for mass, bulk density, and organic carbon content, for example by loss-on-ignition or elemental analysis. Based on sediment accumulation rates and measured carbon concentrations, sedimentation rates and associated carbon inputs can be calculated.

To distinguish carbon sources, stable isotope analysis, for example $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, can be applied to partition autochthonous, locally produced, and allochthonous, river-derived, organic carbon contributions. Measurements are conducted at point locations and can be extrapolated to floodplain or landscape scale based on hydrogeomorphic units and connectivity gradients.

Habitat type: Floodplains, freshwater forested wetlands, riverine wetlands

Compartment: soils

Indicators:

Sediment accretion rate (mm yr^{-1})

Organic carbon burial rate ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$)

Carbon sequestration rate ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$)

C flow: input

<p>Required data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sediment deposition rates (marker horizons or traps) • Bulk density of deposited sediment • Organic carbon content (e.g. LOI, TOC) • Spatial extent of hydrogeomorphic units • Optional: stable isotope data ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) for source attribution • Optional: hydrological data (connectivity, inundation frequency) <p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marker horizons (e.g. feldspar clay pads) or sediment traps • Sampling corers for surface sediment • Drying oven and balance (bulk density) • Laboratory equipment for carbon analysis (LOI furnace or elemental analyzer) • Optional: isotope ratio mass spectrometer 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cost-effective and allows good comparability between sites • Direct quantification of carbon burial, not just biomass growth • Captures both autochthonous and allochthonous carbon inputs • Applicable to large spatial scales via hydrogeomorphic classification • High relevance for wetland carbon accounting • Can achieve relatively high accuracy when combining sediment and carbon measurements • Enables integration of process understanding (hydrology, connectivity) 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires field installations and repeated measurements • Laboratory analysis (carbon content, isotopes) can be resource-intensive • Spatial extrapolation introduces uncertainty • Strong dependence on hydraulic and hydrological variability and connectivity • Short monitoring periods may not capture long-term trends • Potential underestimation where sediment redistribution or erosion occurs, high variability according to exposure and flooding event
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stratify sampling along hydrogeomorphic connectivity gradients • Use sufficient replication across floodplain units • Combine sedimentation measurements with carbon content analysis • Apply isotope analysis where source attribution is relevant • Consider long-term monitoring to capture interannual variability • Integrate hydrological data to improve interpretation of deposition patterns 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Hupp, C. R., Kroes, D. E., Noe, G. B., Schenk, E. R., & Day, R. H. (2019). Sediment trapping and carbon sequestration in floodplains of the lower Atchafalaya Basin, LA: Allochthonous versus autochthonous carbon sources. <i>Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences</i>, 124(3), 663–677. https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JG004533</p>	

RCSF6

Soil core analysis using radioisotope dating

Ute Susanne Kaden

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	day	month	year	decades
-------	-----	-------	------	---------

Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Soil or sediment core analysis provides a method to estimate long-term sediment accretion and organic carbon burial in wetlands. Intact soil cores are collected from representative wetland locations and sectioned into defined depth intervals, commonly 2 cm increments. Each increment is dried, weighed, homogenised, and analysed for bulk density and organic carbon content. Additional nutrient analyses, such as total nitrogen and phosphorus, may be included where nutrient burial is of interest.

Sediment accretion rates are reconstructed using radioisotope dating, most commonly ^{137}Cs and ^{210}Pb . ^{137}Cs is used as a time marker related to atmospheric nuclear fallout, with the maximum activity commonly assigned to 1964. ^{210}Pb dating estimates accretion over approximately the last 100–150 years based on the decline of excess ^{210}Pb activity with depth.

Carbon sequestration rates are calculated by combining accretion rate, bulk density, and organic carbon concentration. This produces carbon accumulation rates, commonly expressed as $\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Habitat type: Floodplains, freshwater wetlands, riverine wetlands

Compartment: soils

Indicators:

Sediment accretion rate (mm yr^{-1})

Organic carbon burial rate ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)

Carbon sequestration rate ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)

C flow: input / long-term accumulation

Required data:

- Soil or sediment core depth intervals
- Bulk density per depth increment
- Organic carbon concentration
- ^{137}Cs activity profile
- ^{210}Pb activity profile
- Optional: total nitrogen and phosphorus
- Optional: land use, hydrology, wetland type, and geomorphic setting

<p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil or sediment corer • Drying oven, balance, Sieve / grinder • CHN analyser • Gamma spectrometry system for ¹³⁷Cs and ²¹⁰Pb analysis 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimates long-term sediment accretion and carbon burial • Provides direct link between sediment accumulation and carbon content • Covers decadal to centennial timescales • Applicable for comparing sites and land-use effects 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires specialised laboratory and isotope analysis • Not suitable for citizen science • Sensitive to sediment disturbance and mixing • Limited spatial representativeness (few cores) • Does not capture short-term dynamics
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use replicated cores across representative wetland units or hydrological gradients • Combine ¹³⁷Cs and ²¹⁰Pb where possible, as they represent different but complementary timescales – report clearly whether rates are based on ¹³⁷Cs, ²¹⁰Pb, or both • Avoid disturbed, eroded, or strongly mixed sediment profiles where possible • Combine with sediment traps or marker horizons if both recent and long-term accretion are relevant 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Craft, C., Vymazal, J., & Kröpfelová, L. (2018). Carbon sequestration and nutrient accumulation in floodplain and depression wetlands. <i>Ecological Engineering</i>, 114, 137–145. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2017.06.034</p>	

RCSF7

Chamber CO₂/CH₄ fluxes

Valentin Dinu, Tudor Racoviceanu

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Quantifying greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes using direct in-situ chamber measurements and discrete air/water sampling to estimate emissions across different wetland strata (vegetated, open water, and bare soil).

Stratifying each subsite into three land cover types: open water (>10 cm depth), vegetated areas (emergent or submerged), and bare areas (exposed soil/sediment).

Distributing 15–20 chamber measurements proportionately across these strata, with a minimum of 3 per stratum.

Deploying floating or static chambers connected to portable infrared gas analysers (e.g., LI-COR 7810) for high-frequency monitoring of CO₂ and CH₄. Measuring for 5 minutes in vegetated/bare areas and 10–15 minutes in open water to capture both diffusive and ebullitive (bubbling) fluxes. Citizen science involvement may be possible for selected static chamber field tasks under expert supervision.

Calculating gas fluxes based on the rate of change of partial pressure within the chamber, chamber volume, surface area, and air temperature. Normalising data by recording solar radiation, atmospheric pressure, and local wind speed.

Habitat type: Inundated, vegetated, and bare soil wetland areas

Compartment: Air–water and air–soil/sediment interfaces

Indicator: CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes; derived annual carbon exchange estimate (e.g. mg C m⁻² h⁻¹; t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

C flow: Output (emissions) or Input (uptake)

Required data:

- Gas concentrations
- air/water temperature
- light intensity (SWR)
- atmospheric pressure
- site coordinates

<p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portable gas analysers • floating/static chambers • 60-mL syringes • 12-mL exetainers • Stopcocks • light/temp sensors • pottery clay for sealing 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct Flux Capture: Quantifies real-time in-situ fluxes and effectively captures CH₄ ebullition (bubbling) events. • Photosynthetic Assessment: Paired dark/transparent chamber measurements in vegetated areas isolate the effect of photosynthesis on gas exchange. • Standardised Comparisons: Integrated sediment core incubations provide potential flux benchmarks under controlled conditions. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather Sensitivity: Measurements are highly sensitive to local meteorological conditions, which can complicate site comparisons. • Labor Intensive: Requires significant field effort, frequent sampling campaigns (every 3 months), and specialised equipment. • Logistical Complexity: Requires high-level technical expertise for instrument calibration and complex gas chromatography lab analysis.
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sealing: Use pottery clay for terrestrial chamber seals; avoid using site-specific wet sediment as it can produce measurement artifacts. • Timing: Always respect the instrument "warm-up" period and record start/end times in UTC to maintain consistency with the gas analyser. • Photosynthesis: Avoid casting shadows on light chambers or sensors during measurements in transparent chambers. • System Disturbance: When sampling in open water, operate from a boat to avoid perturbing the sediment and triggering artificial bubbling. 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Minaudo, C., von Schiller, D., Misteli, B., Morant, D., Adamescu, M., Attermeyer, K., Basset, A., Carballeira, R., Cazacu, C., Coelho, J.P., Guelmami, A., Hilaire, S., Miralles, J., Obrador, B., Petkuvienė, J., Picazo, A., Rochera, C., Santinelli, C., Teixeira, H., Titocci, J., Vaicute, D., Camacho, A. (2023) Methodological manual. Deliverable D4.2 Horizon RESTORE4Cs Project GA ID: 101056782.</p> <p>Reed, C. C., Winters, J. M., Hart, S. C., Hutchinson, R., Chandler, M., Venicx, G., & Sullivan, B. W. (2018). Building flux capacity: Citizen scientists increase resolution of soil greenhouse gas fluxes. <i>PloS one</i>, 13(7), e0198997. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0198997</p>	

RCSF8

ICOS / Fluxnet (eddy covariance flux measurements)

Tudor Racoviceanu, Mihai Adamescu

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

ICOS is a European-wide greenhouse gas research infrastructure. ICOS produces standardised data on greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere, as well as on carbon fluxes between the atmosphere, the earth, and oceans.

The ICOS / Fluxnet method is based on **eddy covariance measurements** to quantify exchanges of greenhouse gases (primarily CO₂ and CH₄) between ecosystems and the atmosphere. Measurements are conducted continuously at fixed monitoring stations equipped with high-frequency sensors. Fluxes are calculated at short time intervals (typically 30 minutes), enabling analysis across multiple temporal scales ranging from hourly dynamics to long-term trends over years and decades.

Spatially, measurements integrate fluxes over a dynamic footprint area determined by atmospheric conditions, typically covering areas from tens to several hundred meters around the installation tower. This corresponds to plot to site scale, with results often interpreted at landscape scale when combined with modeling or upscaling approaches.

The core setup consists of a **3D sonic anemometer** (measuring wind speed and direction) and a **gas analyser** (measuring gas concentrations). These instruments are mounted on a tower above the vegetation canopy to capture turbulent fluxes representative of the ecosystem. Fluxes are calculated from the covariance between vertical wind speed and gas concentration fluctuations at high frequency (typically 10–20 Hz). Raw data is processed using dedicated software to remove errors, fill data gaps, and calculate carbon exchange indicators.

ICOS ensures standardisation across sites through harmonised protocols, calibration routines, and centralised data processing.

Habitat type: all (semi-)terrestrial habitats – forests, grasslands, wetlands, croplands

Compartment: atmosphere – ecosystem interface

Indicator: Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) expressed as $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 / \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, exchange between ecosystem and atmosphere, reported as Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE) **C flow** / carbon exchange (ΔC over time)

<p>Required data and software: Li-Cor Tovi Software</p> <p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eddy covariance tower • 3D sonic anemometer • Infrared gas analyzer (CO₂/H₂O, optionally CH₄) • Data logger and acquisition system • Meteorological sensors (radiation, temperature, humidity, precipitation) • Power supply (grid or solar) • Communication system for data transfer 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct, continuous measurement of ecosystem–atmosphere carbon exchange • Very high temporal resolution (sub-hourly) • Standardised methodology across global networks (ICOS, Fluxnet) • Suitable for long-term trend and carbon budget assessment • Captures ecosystem-scale processes rather than point observations 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very high installation and maintenance costs • Requires specialised expertise for setup, calibration, and data processing • Data gaps due to instrument failure or unsuitable atmospheric conditions • Limited spatial representativeness (flux footprint varies with conditions) • Complex post-processing and uncertainty handling
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure proper site selection (homogeneous fetch, minimal disturbance) • Maintain long-term operation for meaningful carbon budget assessment • Apply standardised ICOS / Fluxnet processing protocols • Combine flux measurements with biomass or soil carbon observations for better interpretation • Regular calibration and maintenance are critical for data quality 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>https://www.icos-cp.eu/</p> <p>https://fluxnet.org/</p> <p>https://www.licor.com/products/eddy-covariance/tovi</p>	

RCSF9

Tea bag index

Jana Borovská, Lubos Halada, Tudor Racoviceanu, Valentin Dinu

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs
	€			

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	day	month	year	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

The Tea Bag Index is a standardised field method for estimating early-stage organic matter decomposition and stabilisation in soils. Standard tea bags (Lipton green tea and/or rooibos) are buried in the upper soil layer and retrieved after a defined incubation period, commonly around 90 days. Degradation-resistant woven nylon bags are preferred over non-woven PET bags.

The initial weight of dry tea bags is measured before burial (tea and bags; M1), using a scale with at least two decimal places (0.01 g). Plastic labels are added to the tea bags. Triplicates are used and buried separately in 8 cm deep holes, 15 cm apart. Labels should remain visible above the soil, and the burial site should be marked for later retrieval. Environmental conditions such as vegetation, shading, and humus layer should be described.

After retrieval, adhering soil particles are removed by hand. The tea bags are dried by air drying or oven drying (max. 68°C/48 h). The weight of dried tea bags is then measured as: 1. tea in the bag (without the label on the string; M2), 2. empty bag (M3), and 3. pure tea from the bag (M4). The initial weight of pure tea is calculated as $M0 = M1 - M3$.

Mass loss of the tea material is used to calculate decomposition-related indicators, including the decomposition rate constant (k), stabilisation factor (S), and percentage mass loss. The decomposition rate is calculated for each bag and averaged for each triplicate.

Habitat type: all not flooded terrestrial habitats; if tropical conditions shorten the burial time to 60 days

Compartment: upper soil layer (A-horizon)

Indicator:

decomposition rate constant (k , day⁻¹)

stabilisation factor (S , unitless)

mass loss (% or g g⁻¹ over time)

C flow: output

<p>Required data: site conditions, meteorological characteristics</p> <p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lipton Indonesian tea Sencha tradition: EAN 87 22700 05552 5 • Lipton Infusion Rooibos: 5 063270 101612 • analytical balance (0.01 or .001 g) 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard material (Lipton green and rooibos tea) provides a uniform substrate for comparison across sites. • Non-degradable nylon mesh bags reduce methodological bias from decomposition of the bag material. • Simple and low-cost field experiment with low technical barriers. • Suitable for citizen science with basic training. • Useful indicator of soil biological activity and early-stage organic matter decomposition. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific tea bags used in global decomposition studies are not always available. • Use of replacement bags may affect comparability and requires checking mesh size and material properties. • Represents decomposition of standard material, not site-specific litter. • Does not directly quantify carbon sequestration or carbon fluxes
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In case of planned chemical analyses, powder-free nitril gloves should be worn. • Lipton tea was used in global multi-site experiments. In local studies without the ambition to compare to global results, other types of tea could be used. • The time course of decomposition can be studied using a larger number of tea bags buried for different periods of time – e.g. 3 months, 6 months, 9 months, 1 year, 1.5 years, 2 years. 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Djukic, I., Kepfer-Rojas, S., Schmidt, I. K., Larsen, K. S., Beier, C., Berg, B., ... & Alatalo, J. (2018). Early stage litter decomposition across biomes. <i>Science of the total environment</i>, 628, 1369–1394. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.01.012</p> <p>Keuskamp, J.A., Dingemans, B.J.J., Lehtinen, T., Sarneel, J.M. and Hefting, M.M. (2013), Tea Bag Index: a novel approach to collect uniform decomposition data across ecosystems. <i>Methods Ecol Evol</i>, 4: 1070–1075. https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12097</p> <p>Kwon, T., Shibata, H., Kepfer-Rojas, S., Schmidt, I. K., Larsen, K. S., Beier, C., Berg, B., Verheyen, K., Lamarque, J.-F., Hagedorn, F., Eisenhauer, N., & Djukic, I. (2021). Effects of Climate and Atmospheric Nitrogen Deposition on Early to Mid-Term Stage Litter Decomposition Across Biomes. <i>Frontiers in Forests and Global Change</i>, 4. https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2021.678480</p> <p>Tea Bag Index App: https://citizenscience.eu/project/618</p> <p>Wagner, M., Ahrends, B., & Meesenburg, H. (2017). Die Teebeutel-Methode als Instrument globaler, standardisierter Streuabbaueversuche. <i>Waldböden: Nutzung und Schutz</i>, 99. (https://www.nwfva.de/fileadmin/nwfva/publikationen/pdf/wagner_2017_die_teebeutelmethode_als2.pdf)</p>	

RCSF10

Litter traps

Valentin Dinu, Tudor Racoviceanu

Field Measurement

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

Litter trap monitoring quantifies aboveground litterfall (e.g. leaves, twigs, reproductive material) as a key pathway of carbon and nutrient transfer from vegetation to the soil surface. Standardised traps (e.g. 0.5 m²) are installed above ground to collect falling litter, often complemented by ground-based collection areas for larger debris.

Traps are typically constructed using PVC frames with mesh screens forming a basin to retain litter while allowing water drainage. Installations must be level and positioned representatively across the study site.

Litter is collected at regular intervals (e.g. monthly or biweekly), transferred to labeled containers, dried to constant mass (e.g. 65°C), and sorted into categories (leaves, wood, reproductive parts, other). Dry mass is determined for each category and summed to estimate total litterfall.

Annual litterfall rates are calculated and expressed per unit area (e.g. Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). If carbon concentration is measured or assumed, litterfall can be converted to carbon input (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹).

Habitat type: Forests (tropical and temperate)

Compartment: Above-ground (vegetation to soil surface)

Indicators:

Annual litterfall production (Mg dry mass ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

Aboveground litter carbon input (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, if carbon content is included)

Nutrient return via litterfall (optional; e.g. kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

C flow: Input

Required data:

- Dry weight per litter category
- Collection interval (days)
- Trap area
- Site coordinates and forest type

<p>Required equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PVC pipes and connectors (e.g. 15 mm diameter) • Mesh screen (e.g. 1.2 mm) • Support structures (e.g. rebar/stakes) • Wire ties • Cloth collection bags • Permanent markers • Drying oven (e.g. 65°C) • Electronic balance (≥ 0.1 g accuracy) 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Retention: Deep mesh basins prevent wind from blowing litter out while ensuring efficient water drainage. • Sample Purity: Elevated design (80 cm) prevents soil and mud splash-back, ensuring clean samples for chemical analysis. • Total Capture: Paired ground/above-ground systems capture the full spectrum of debris, from tiny seeds to large palm fronds. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Maintenance: Screens are fragile; approximately 25% require annual replacement due to debris impact or wear. • Labor Intensive: Requires significant manual effort for frequent collection and sorting into four distinct botanical categories.
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slopes: On uneven terrain, tailor-cut the PVC legs (shorter uphill, longer downhill) to keep the trap frame perfectly level. • Safety: Wear a filter mask when sorting dried litter to avoid inhaling dust or mold. • Maintenance: Inspect window screens regularly for holes and repair with patches as needed. • Visibility: Paint ground traps fluorescent orange to make them easier to locate under fresh litterfall/ or one can use coloured flags to help you spot the traps. • Citizen Scientists may support regular trap checks, litter collection, labelling, and site documentation after basic training. Drying, sorting, weighing, carbon analysis, and interpretation should remain supervised to ensure data quality. 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Muller-Landau, H. C., & Wright, S. J. (2010). Litterfall Monitoring Protocol. <i>CTFS Global Forest Carbon Research Initiative</i>.</p> <p>Pitman, R., Bastrup-Birk, A. M., Bréda, N., & Rautio, P. (2010). Sampling and analysis of litterfall. <i>Manual on methods and criteria for harmonized sampling, assessment, monitoring and analysis of the effects of air pollution on forests: Part XIII</i>.</p>	

RCSG1

Land-cover-based C-sequestration assessments / InVEST model

Marie Wahl, Maja Novković

Geospatial analysis

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs
	€			

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	days	months	years	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

The carbon content stored in different land cover / land use (LCLU) types within a study site is estimated using the InVEST® model “Carbon Storage and Sequestration”. The model requires input data on four carbon pools (above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, soil carbon, and dead organic matter) for each LCLU class. Carbon stocks are calculated by assigning carbon values to each class and aggregating them across the spatial extent of the study area based on land use maps.

The outputs are spatially explicit raster datasets representing carbon stocks, which can be further processed in GIS software and MS Excel to derive total carbon storage values. If land cover maps from different time steps (past or projected future scenarios) are provided, the model estimates linear changes in carbon stocks between these time points. This change can be interpreted as carbon sequestration or loss over the specified period.

Habitat type: all (semi-)terrestrial habitats

Compartment: soils / biomass

Indicator: Change in carbon stock (ΔC ; t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

C flow: delta

Required data and software:

- Land cover / land use maps (CORINE LC and/or Riparian Zones from Copernicus) of two different years
- Carbon pool values for at least one carbon pool (above-ground, below-ground, dead organic matter and/or soil organic carbon)
- Information on climate region and soil types
- Software: InVEST Workbench, GIS software (e.g. QGIS, ArcGIS), MS Excel

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Straightforward and transparent workflow • Versatility of the carbon pool data sources • Allows comparison of carbon pools between different habitat types • Allows prediction of future carbon sequestration potential of the area • Allows overview of the past carbon storage pools of the area • Enables coarse insight into carbon pools trends for the area 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model oversimplifies natural carbon cycle and assumes a linear change in carbon sequestration rates over time • The Riparian Zones model does not cover all target areas • Corine Land Cover model could be coarse for complex ecosystems such as riparian wetlands • Depending on the expert knowledge about the assessment area • Scarce info about specific habitat/vegetation type storage capacities in the literature
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is a prerequisite for the user to have basic knowledge in MS Excel and in GIS mapping software, like QGIS or ArcGIS. • It is recommended to use the model for assessing carbon stocks instead of carbon sequestration. Model only relies on land cover or land use changes and does not account for carbon sequestration rates over time in an unchanged landscape. 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>InVEST: https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest</p> <p>Wahl, M. (2025). Assessing carbon stocks using the Invest Model – Guidelines and templates. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17371707</p>	

RCSG2

Above-ground carbon stock change estimation using LiDAR, spectral indices and elevation data

Andrei Toma

Geospatial analysis

Citizen Science	Accuracy	Expertise	Time	Costs

Process-scale

Temporal

hours	day	month	year	decades
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Spatial

sample	plot	habitat type	site	landscape
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General approach

This method estimates spatially continuous above-ground biomass (AGB) by integrating GEDI L4A footprint data with spectral indices from Landsat imagery and terrain information from SRTM DEM. A U-Net deep learning model is applied within a cloud-based workflow using Google Earth Engine and Google Colab.

Extract GEDI AGB points; compute spectral indices (EVI, NDMI, NDBI) and elevation from Landsat/SRTM in Google Earth Engine; sample GEDI points; train a U-Net model in Google Colab to predict biomass at scale.

When applied to multi-temporal datasets, the method allows estimation of changes in above-ground biomass between time steps. These changes can be converted to above-ground carbon stock change (ΔC), which can serve as a proxy for above-ground carbon sequestration over the observation period.

Habitat type: forests

Compartment: above-ground biomass

Indicator:

Above-ground biomass (AGB; Mg ha^{-1})

Change in AGB (Mg ha^{-1} over time period)

Above-ground carbon stock change (ΔC ; t C ha^{-1} over time period)

C flow: delta

Required data:

- GEDI L4A AGB footprint data
- Landsat imagery (for spectral indices: EVI, NDMI, NDBI)
- SRTM DEM (elevation data)

Required equipment:

- Google Earth Engine
- Google Colab or equivalent environment for model training
- GIS software (optional, e.g. QGIS or ArcGIS for post-processing)

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and globally available datasets (GEDI, Landsat, SRTM) • Cloud-based workflow (no high-performance local hardware required) • Deep learning approach (U-Net) captures spatial patterns effectively • Flexible and scalable across regions • Integration of structural, spectral, and topographic information 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes between time steps may reflect model or input data uncertainties rather than actual biomass dynamics • Sparse GEDI coverage (no wall-to-wall sampling) • Temporal misalignment between GEDI and Landsat data • Cloud masking limitations affecting spectral data quality • Model transferability between regions may be limited without retraining • Estimates represent above-ground biomass only; belowground and soil carbon are not included
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure consistency in input data, preprocessing steps, and model configuration across time steps when assessing changes • Apply the same trained model or carefully validate model transferability for multi-temporal analysis • Align datasets seasonally to avoid biases due to phenological differences • Convert AGB to carbon using appropriate conversion factors (e.g. ~0.45–0.5), and report assumptions • Interpret results as above-ground carbon stock change (ΔC) and not as full ecosystem carbon sequestration • Combine with complementary methods (e.g. soil carbon measurements or flux observations) for a more complete carbon balance assessment 	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Toma, A., Cvijanovic, D., Tschikof, M., & Scrieciu, A. (2025). ABOVE-GROUND C-STOCK ESTIMATES USING LIDAR, SPECTRAL INDICES AND ELEVATION DATA. Restore4Life Protocol. Zenodo. https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703465</p>	